

LOCALIZED APPARATUS IN TEACHING GEOMETRICAL OPTICS

Localized Apparatus in Teaching Geometrical Optics

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By

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the performance of the students about the basic concepts of geometrical optics before and after participating in the localized apparatus demonstrations and experiments. The respondents that demonstrate the set-up and who will answer the pretest and posttest are the grade 11 students from the Senior High School class of Sampiniton Provincial Community High School. The researcher utilized the quasi-experimental design, pretest–posttest design, in the study. Wherein, learners were randomly assigned to either (1) experimental or (2) control group. Both groups were pretested for the independent variable. The experimental group received the treatment where they performed the activity using the localized apparatus in teaching geometrical optics. Both groups were post tested to examine the effects of manipulating the independent variable on the dependent variable. The study revealed that localized apparatus used in the experiment is both accurate and consistent in demonstrating the concepts on geometrical optics. Furthermore, there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students in all the topics on the concepts of geometrical optics. The study revealed that the localized apparatus is effective in improving the performance of the students on the concepts of geometrical optics.

Keywords: Localized apparatus, geometrical optics, students' performance

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Chapter I

The Problem and Its Scope

Introduction

The Department of Education in its effort to improve quality education implemented the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum (EBEC) in pursuant to Section 16 of Republic Act No. 10533, entitled “An act enhancing the Philippine basic education system by strengthening its curriculum and increasing the number of years for basic education, appropriating funds therefore and for other purposes,” otherwise known as the “Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013” (Republic Act 10533).

“The curriculum shall use spiral progression approach to ensure mastery of knowledge and skills after each levels” as well as the implementing rules and regulations stating that “the curriculum shall be contextualized and global and shall be flexible enough to be able and allow schools to be localized, indigenous and enhance the same based on their respective educational context” (Rule II, Curriculum Section 10.10.3 of the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum of 2013). Localization and contextualization is the new approach to learning as highlighted in the K-to-12 curriculum.

Bringas (2014) gives important reminders on contextualization and localization stating that localization and contextualization can be done in all learning areas: in localization, teachers maximize materials, activities, events, and issues that are readily available in the local environment, while in contextualization,

teachers must use authentic materials and anchor teaching in the context of learners' lives.

Based on the study entitled "On Designing and Evaluating Teaching Sequences Taking Geometrical Optics as an Example" that describes and discusses how the research program has been implemented in the area of geometrical optics at the upper level (grades 8 and 9) of compulsory school, it was suggested that the idea of content-oriented theories is worth further examination and development and might contribute to strengthening science education as an autonomous discipline (Andersson, B. and Bach, F., 2005).

Geometrical optics is one of the core topics in physics instruction in lower secondary. Numerous learning difficulties and students' conceptions have been identified by physics education research during the last decades (Duit, 2009). What seems to be another frequent problem is that instruction in geometrical optics treats optical phenomena quite soon on an abstract level focusing on the construction of ray diagrams without taking the actual phenomena and related beams of light holistically into account (Wiesner, Engelhardt, & Herdt, 1995).

The following discussion presents the theories, concepts, insights, generalizations, and ideas which aided and inspired the researcher to examine the effect of contextualization and localization in teaching geometrical optics to students' performance in contrast to the conventional ray diagramming. This paper is anchored on the effect of the contextualized and localized teaching on the students' performance. The simplified construction; fun, innovated activities; and

low-cost readily available materials are specially designed to make the lesson more interactive with actual hands-on activities.

Theoretical Background of the Study

This study is anchored on the experiential learning theory (KLT), where David A. Kolb believes that learning is the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience (Kolb, 1984). The foundation in constructing the concepts in making improvised materials for geometrical optics is firmly rooted in this theory. Kolb's experiential learning theory is composed of four equally important stages; these are the concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation (David L., 2007). Note that since each stage is equally important, the process may start in any stage, but it should follow the sequence as indicated in Figure 1.

Concrete experience. In this stage, another experience or circumstance is experienced, or a reinterpretation of existing knowledge is done (McLeod, 2017). Education that happens due to direct involvement in the events of life (Houle, 1980) might be described as experiential learning. Such pattern starts with concrete experience, with individuals getting things done (Smith, 1988). This may be in a form of a class activity like field works or lab sessions (JL, 2007).

The researcher found out that teaching optics has been focused with lectures, diagrams, and video clips. Hence, when the inexpensive set-ups for demonstrations and experiments were presented to the learners, learning will not be just interesting but also meaningful to them since there will be direct involvement and manipulation in the activity.

Reflective observation. In this stage, learners will refine the concept learned through reflection. This is done by dividing the concept into two separate learning activities, perceiving and processing (Technology, 1996).

In relation to the study conducted, the use of the inexpensive set-up for geometrical optics will enable the learners to reflect about their previous concepts learned and connect it to the new concepts learned which will result to the reflection and change in the perception about the geometrical optics. This will allow the learners to assimilate the old knowledge from the new one.

Abstract conceptualization. In the critical reflection stage, we tend to ask and reflect the previous knowledge and contrast it to the new ones. In the abstract conceptualization stage, learners try seeking for the answer, construct generalizations, state conclusions, and may later form hypotheses about the experience (Kelly, 1997).

Since new knowledge was created, formation of model and/or new theory may be formed. Learners will discern concepts that are weak leading them to form new models or create modification. In the study conducted, learners in this stage have understood the broad concepts of optics with the help of the inexpensive demonstrations and experiments, and this will enable them to answer the questions in the experiment guide.

Active experimentation. Learning in this stage takes a functioning structure since learners are engaged into experimenting, affecting or changing circumstances (Kolb, 1984), and apply it to real-world situations to see what will be the result (McLeod, 2013).

In the study that was conducted, the inexpensive demonstration and experiment of the set-up was tested against the concepts learned from lectures. Learners validated the validity of the ray diagramming technique against the inexpensive set-up. Transmission of concepts then followed when new concepts learned from the experiment were applied to situations or activities in the actual world where the concepts of optics are applied. Positive results in the learner's posttest proved evident to this stage.

In this connection and in relation to the study, active participation and cooperation among students and actual manipulation of the inexpensive device led to students' learning. The experience provided by the hands-on manipulation, calculations, data recording, and reporting of the results of the experiments provided concrete learning, eliminating misconceptions and negative perceptions about geometrical optics. These concepts will not be appreciated by just a plain lecture, video clip presentation, and /or ray diagramming alone.

The Kolb model is termed an experiential learning model to emphasize the important part that experience is essential in the learning process, an emphasis which differentiates this approach from other cognitive theories of the process of learning (Kolb, 1976). The very root of the cycle is a simple description of learning: Concepts are translated from what the learner have experienced, then to the reflection and assessment of the new knowledge from the old one, and to the conceptualization of what have been learned which will then result to active experimentation.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework of the study based on Kolb's experiential learning theory (1984)

Review of Related Literature and Studies

The researcher has searched studies from local and international researches, journals, and articles to support the study. The following are presented in the following paragraphs.

Improvisation of instructional materials. The instructional materials utilized in K-12 science classes give the premise to what learners can acquire and what teachers should be teaching. The procedure used to choose those materials is essential to furnishing learners and teachers with a strong foundation for accomplishment and effective teaching. With the absence of the standardized instructional material, teacher must device improvised instructional materials to help facilitate learning as much as the standardized ones.

Since Philippine public schools could not provide all the instructional laboratory materials needed in the laboratories, the science teachers and the learners need to make use of what they innovate or create from locally available materials (Johnson, 2000). Improvisation therefore would be the alternative means for the teacher to provide the sufficient apparatus for the learners.

Accuracy of measurement from the apparatus. Percentage of errors can determine how big errors are when measuring something in an experiment. Furthermore, it can tell how badly unavoidable errors are in the experiment. Stephanie (2018) stressed that smaller values mean closer to the computed value.

In a study conducted by Adedayo J.O. entitled "Validating the Use of Improvised Materials in Determining the Value of Acceleration Due to Gravity" where he used the standard and improvised sets of apparatus in determining the

value of acceleration due to gravity, he finds out that the two sets of experiments showed close comparative values. He then concluded that improvised scientific materials should be accepted as being reliable just like the standard apparatus (Adedayo, 2018).

On the other hand, Eduardo Pérez, in his study entitled “A Precise, Simple, and Low-Cost Experiment to Determine the Isobaric Expansion Coefficient for Physical Chemistry Students” that uses a low-cost materials in determining isobaric expansion coefficient, suggests that the precision and accuracy in the measurements were not forfeited (Pérez,2015).

Consistency of measurement from the apparatus. A study conducted by Maxino (2016) in Physics Education Center of Maxino College, Dumaguete City, where two versions of an inexpensive optical reflection apparatus are presented shows high acceptability and reliability of the apparatus (Philippine Physics Journal, 2016).

In another study about optics entitled “Locally-Constructed Apparatus for Reflection and Refraction of Light Experiments” conducted by R.G. Tubog and B. A. Piñero, wherein they used inexpensive 5mm clear blue LED in a simple device to produce a fine stream of light in a reflection of light experiment, it was concluded that “the constructed apparatus is accurate and very reliable in reflection of light experiment (Tubog & Piñero, 2018). The locally constructed apparatus is good and ideal in explaining and demonstrating the laws of reflection of light.

Escalante etal. (2018)conducted a study entitled “An Inexpensive Method in Determining the Index of Refraction of Water.” The study suggests that in

determining the index of refraction of water, expensive equipment is not a requirement. Readily available materials can be used in determining the index of refraction of water and can be replicated inside the classrooms without the need of high-end equipment. The outcome of the study gave comparable result to the standard value (Philippine Physics Journal, 2018).

Another study entitled "Inexpensive Free Fall Apparatus" conducted by Tubog and Piñero (2016) that aims to design a locally made and inexpensive apparatus that would demonstrate free fall suggests that the apparatus is accurate and reliable as compared to the generally accepted value of the acceleration due to gravity (Philippine Physics Journal, 2016). A study entitled "Improvised Loop the Loop Track: Demonstration and Investigation of the Minimum Launching Heights" by Victoria M. Ruguian (2016) was conducted in explaining the principle of conservation of energy. Ruguian suggests that the improvised apparatus can be used by teachers to visualize and demonstrate the principles of conservation of energy (Philippine Physics Journal, 2016).

Furthermore, the Department of Physics of Mapua Institute of Technology Intramuros, Manila, with Cuan (2004) conducted a relevant study entitled "Construction of an Improvised Apparatus for Determination of Permittivity of Free Space" which target to develop and devise an improvised apparatus used to measure the permittivity of free space of zero (0), which is a fundamental constant in the field of electrostatics. The result of the experiment shows constant 0 percentage error which is favorable.

In relation to the study, the researcher is committed to ensuring that the data gathered from demonstration and experiment of the inexpensive localized apparatus will be consistent all throughout the study. Without consistency of measurements from the demonstrations and experiments, it will be hard to arrive with the correct insight of the concept on geometrical optics.

The researcher has made some considerations; percentage of error by the students is less than 10% due to some considerable error that may occur in the construction, calibration, and operation of the device (Swamy et al., 2017).

Conceptual understanding of geometrical optics. In terms of knowledge competencies, conceptual understanding and the concepts in science are inseparable parts since conceptual understanding is one of the basic competencies in science learning. Therefore, in order for the learners to learn science successfully, conceptual understanding is needed (Widiyatmoko and Shimizu, 2018). Students with a sound conceptual understanding will integrate the knowledge into long-term memory (Gabel, 2003).

“Conceptual” is something other than the capacity to know the connections among things (Sands, 2014). By means of conceptual understanding, learners are able to grasp the ideas better, thus allowing them to integrate the concept learned into different subjects. Concepts are not easily forgotten by the learners, and it allows the attainment of high learner engagement, collaboration among themselves, metacognition, and higher-order thinking skills (Omari & Chen, 2016; Schwartz 2010; Learn Implement Share, 2017).

Student's ability can be developed if students are given practice, where reasoning is involved. If students are involved in the actual manipulation of important concepts, they can significantly deepen their understanding of even very difficult material (Paula R.L. Heron).

The study by Even, Balland, and Guillet (n.d.) entitled "Learning Through Experimenting: An Original Way of Teaching Geometrical Optics" concluded that students learn through experimenting, wherein geometrical optics is taught in a modern and interactive way where students are encouraged to be more active than in a classical course.

In the study, the conceptual understanding on the concept of geometrical optics is greatly emphasized wherein the connection of the previously acquired knowledge and the present knowledge has given importance. The inexpensive apparatus and the design of the activity have taken into emphasis to ensure clear and accurate delivery in the concept on geometrical optics.

The following are some concepts where students can integrate in understanding the concepts in geometrical optics.

Law of Reflection. Reflection is when light bounces off an object. Smooth and shiny surfaces, like glass, water, or polished metal reflect light at the same angle as it hit the surface (Science Learn, 2012). The light wave coming from the light source is referred to as an incident wave, and the wave that is bounced away from the surface of the mirror is referred to as the reflected wave. The angle of incidence is equal to the angle of reflection for visible light. This concept is often termed the Law of Reflection (Fellers & Davidson, 2018)

Nature and Properties of Light. The speed of light traveling in a vacuum is 2.99×10^8 m/s which is considered universal. It is important to know that the speed of light could change when it travels in a non-vacuum medium such as glass and water. Light energy can behave like a wave as it moves through space, or it can behave like a discrete particle with a discrete amount of energy (quantum) that can be absorbed and emitted. The particle nature of light is modeled with photons that have no charge and mass. Photon is a carrier of electromagnetic energy and interacts with other particles such as electrons, atoms, and molecules (Bayeh, C. Z., 2001).

Snell's Law of Reflection. In optics, there is a relationship between the path taken by a ray of light in crossing the boundary or surface of separation between two contacting substances and the refractive index of each. Snell's law relates to the degree of the bending of light to the properties of the refractive material. This law is basic to modern geometrical optics (Vandergriff, 2016).

Nature of Images. Images with mirrors are formed when many nonparallel rays from a given point on a source are reflected from the mirror surface, converge, and form a corresponding image point. When this happens, point by point for an extended object, an image of the object, point by point, is formed. Just as the law of reflection determines the imaging properties of mirrors, Snell's law of refraction determines the imaging properties of lenses. Lenses are essentially light-controlling elements, used primarily for image formation with visible light, but also for ultraviolet and infrared light (Pedrotti, 2001).

Thin lenses: convex lens. A lens is called converging lens if both sides of the lens bend outward and allow the light from distant objects to bend inward toward a common point, called the focal point (Khan Academy,2018).

The axis of a lens is the line drawn through the centers of curvature of its refracting surfaces. If a beam of rays parallel to the axis is incident on a converging lens, the beam is conveyed to focus at a point on the axis called the focal point (F), while the distance along the axis from the focal point to the center of the lens is known as the focal length (f) (Serway & Vuille,2015).

A virtual image is a reproduction of an object via light that is formed where the light rays cross when projected back from their path beyond a lens or mirror. A virtual image only exists within the brain of the observer but is said to exist at the perceived point of intersection (chegg).On the other hand, the image in which light rays from one point of the object actually cross at the location of the image and can be projected onto a screen, a piece of film, or the retina of an eye is called a real image (courses.lumenlearning).

The lens equation that is used to mathematically describe the orientation and nature of an image formed by a lens can be expressed as follows: $1/u + 1/v = 1/f$, where u is the distance of the object and v is for the distance of the image from the lens, respectively; f on the other hand stands for the focal length of the lens (Williams, 2010)

Curved mirrors: concave mirror. Mirrors that have curved surfaces that reflect the light rays are called curved mirrors. Basically these curved surfaces are parts of spherical surfaces, and hence they are also called as spherical mirrors

(Physics Tutor Vista, 2018). Objects reflected in concave mirrors appear to form bigger images than what they really are, although the characteristics of the image depend upon the distance of the object from the mirror (Telsch, 2018).

The mirror equation relates the image distance to the object distance and the focal length. The mirror equation is $1/f = 1/d_o + 1/d_i$ where the variable d_o represents the object distance or the distance between the mirror surface and the object, the variable d_i represents the image distance or the distance between the mirror surface and the image, and the variable f stands for the focal length of the mirror (The Physics Classroom, 2018).

Binoculars and telescopes make use of convex lenses to magnify objects making them appear closer, but convex lenses do not transfer light precisely, thus creating distortions and blurs (Turnbull, 2013).

Impact of localized instructional materials. This study is conducted to identify locally available materials that can be used in laboratory activities to facilitate an improvement in student's understanding and performance. In this regard, studies are cited to support the purpose and the effectiveness of this study.

A host of researchers have proven the validity and reliability of improvised apparatus in scientific endeavors. Zarewa (2005) observed that students taught with improvised materials performed better than those taught without such materials in physics. Amina (2011) also realized that 98% of the learners who were being shown a rate of transpiration in plant with improvised photometer have a passing rate during the test, while only 15% of the control group scores a passing rate in the test.

Just recently, a study on improvised instructional materials in fluid mechanics was conducted by Patron (2017) entitled “Inexpensive Demonstrations and Experiments for Fluid Mechanics” that aimed to determine the performance of the students before participating in the inexpensive demonstrations and experiments and the performance of the students about the simple concept of fluid mechanics after participating in the inexpensive demonstrations and experiments.

The study then concluded that there is an improvement in the students’ performance in understanding the basic concepts of fluid mechanics which is attributed to the inexpensive demonstration and experiment. The findings of Patron is supported by the study of Olagunju (2000) and Nwike(2013) where they found out that the performance of the students after being subjected to intervention activity shows a positive result.

Similarly, the study of Yucor (2018) reveals that significant differences exist between the pretest and posttest performances of the students after using a localized apparatus in their experiment in teaching cosine laws.

Another study, entitled “Effect of Improvised Instructional Materials on Students’ Achievement in Geometry at the Upper Basic Education Level in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria,” finds out that students taught with improvised instructional materials improved on their geometry achievement wherein both male learners and female learners in the experimental group improved more on their geometry achievement than those of the control group (Clement, 2014)

In the study conducted by Olejado et al. entitled “Instructional Materials and Students’ Academic Achievement in Physics: Some Policy Implications,” it was

revealed that there is a significant difference in the achievement of students taught using standard instructional materials, those taught with improvised instructional material, and those in the conventional instruction. The researchers conclude that the utilization of improvised instructional materials promote and enhance effective teaching–learning process (Oladejo, 2011).

In contrast, the study of Onasanya and Omosewo (2011) entitled “Effects of Improvised and Standard Instructional Materials on Secondary School Students’ Academic Performance in Physics in Ilorin, Nigeria” revealed that the use of improvised instructional materials in physics shows no significant difference after testing both the controlled and the experimental group of students.

Conceptual Background of the Study

The focus of the study is to construct and design an activity on inexpensive set-ups for demonstrations and experiments using materials that are readily available locally. This aims to help students understand and concretize the concepts of geometrical optics. The process of the study follows as presented in Figure 2.

The process begins with the Input; here the experiment Guides and Construction Guides for Optics are created as based on the Junior High School’s Science 10 Learners’ Manual for Unit 2: Module 3 entitled Light: Lenses and Mirrors.

The next part is the process. This part contains the pretest, inexpensive set-ups for demonstrations and experiments used as interventions, and ends with a posttest to check how much the learners have learned from the topic. The output is the last part of the process where it is expected that the learners have improved understanding of concepts on geometrical optics

Figure 2. Diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the performance of the learners about the basic concepts of geometrical optics before and after participating in the demonstrations and experiments using localized apparatus. Specifically, this study intended to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the accuracy of the set-up in the demonstrations and experiments for:
 - 1.1. Thin lenses: convex lens;
 - 1.2. Curved mirror: concave mirror; and
 - 1.3. Plane mirror: law of reflection?
2. How consistent is the set-up in measuring the:
 - 2.1 Focal length of the lens and the mirror;
 - 2.2 Size of the image formed (orientation and the size) by the concave mirror and the convex lens; and
 - 2.3 Angle of reflection in a plane mirror with respect to the angle of incidence.
3. What is the pretest performance of the following groups of students:
 - 3.1 Control group; and
 - 3.2 Experimental group?
4. What is the posttest performance of the following groups of students:
 - 4.1 Control group; and
 - 4.2 Experimental group?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students?

6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will benefit the following:

Learners. Learners will display new sets of skills (a) in following the procedures in doing the activity and (b) in observing the image formed from thin lenses, curved and plain mirrors; (c) mathematical skill will also be improved by solving the distance of the image formed and in solving for the focal length of the thin lenses and curved mirror; (d) most importantly, learners will also improve their understanding on the basic concepts of geometrical optics.

Science teachers. They will be able to facilitate the activity more easily with the help of the guides that are simplified and localized. The use of inexpensive materials for the activity will not only make the instructional materials available but also allow the teachers to do more localized and contextualized materials that will facilitate effective and efficient teaching demonstrations and experiments.

School heads. Problems on lack or insufficiency of instructional materials will effectively be minimized with the use of constructed localized instructional materials. Peer coaching and providing technical assistance to teachers and school

head within the school can be intensified to promote effective teaching and learning process.

Public schools. With the help of the administration, schools can maximize the use of the locally available materials in making more instructional materials for the teachers. Learning action cell can be intensified by providing lectures and workshops on the construction and designing of inexpensive instructional materials. Lastly, the problem on the availability of instructional materials will be aided creating more positive performance among teachers and the students per se.

Private schools. The administration of the private schools may conduct seminars and trainings to their teachers with less teaching experience and less skills in the construction and utilization of inexpensive instructional materials. Partnership between public and private school teachers can be strengthened by sharing expertise in using and constructing inexpensive instructional materials, thus, providing better learning to the learners.

Scope and limitations of the study. This study is focused on the performance of the grade 11 students before and after the use of the localized apparatus on the concepts of geometrical optics which include the thin lenses: convex lens, curved mirror, concave mirror, and laws of reflection in plain mirror. This will also test the efficacy of the inexpensive instructional materials in the demonstration and in the experiment.

Limitations of the study. The study is limited only to specific concepts of geometrical optics which are specifically used in the grade 10 curriculum on optics entitled "Mirrors and Lenses." The study used a test questionnaire to measure the

extent of conceptual understanding before and after their use of the set-ups.

However, the researcher does not have any control on the honesty of the answers of the students as well as their internal motivation to participate in the classroom activity. Further, locally made set-ups cannot compare to the accuracy of standard factory apparatuses, but it can still demonstrate the theory. Also, the skills and experience of the students in handling procedures in an experiment can be a limitation to attaining very accurate and consistent measurements; thus it can be considered as a limitation of the present study.

Delimitations of the study. This study confined itself to specific concepts of geometrical optics which is specifically used in the grade 10 curriculum on optics entitled “Mirrors and Lenses”. These concepts are as follows: the concepts of convex lens for thin lenses, concave mirrors for curved mirrors, and the laws of reflection.

Research Methodology

Research design. The researcher utilized the quasi-experimental design, pretest–posttest design, in the study, wherein learners were randomly selected to be assigned in the (1) control or (2) experimental group. Both groups were pretested to ensure that the knowledge of the two groups of students is more or less the same. The result of the pretest was utilized as the independent variable in the study. The experimental group received the treatment where they performed the activity using the localized apparatus in teaching geometrical optics. Both groups were post tested to examine the effects of manipulating the independent variable on the dependent variable (McLeod, 2007). Furthermore, the set-ups used in the

localized apparatus experiments were designed by the researcher basing on the theories and concepts of geometrical optics.

Research environment. The set-ups were made out from locally available materials in the school science laboratory of Sampiniton Provincial Community High School. The testing, demonstration, and experiment were done by the grade 11 senior high school students of Sampiniton Provincial Community High School with a population of 31 students.

The school is a 1-hectare public secondary high school, and it is situated at the hinterlands of Barangay Bantolinao, Manjuyod, Negros Oriental. The school has 13 classrooms, 8 of which are for the junior high school and 4 are for the senior high school. The junior high school faculty is composed of 2 Science teachers, 3 Mathematics teachers, 1 Filipino teacher, 1 English teacher, 1 Araling Panlipunan teacher, and 1 TLE teacher. One grade 10 classroom serves as the school's science laboratory.

Research respondents. The respondents of the study were the grade 11 students from the senior high school class of Sampiniton Provincial Community High School.

The research respondents were randomly selected by simple random sampling. Prior performances were considered in insuring the learners' prior knowledge. Since the study involves small sample, a t-test for independent data was used. The class was divided into two groups, the controlled (15 students) and the experimental groups (16 students). Each group demonstrated the concept separately, wherein the controlled group used the conventional ray diagramming

technique and the experimental group used the localized apparatus and set-up. The controlled group was divided into four groups and was subjected to plain discussion and ray diagramming technique. On the other hand, the experimental group was subjected to the localized apparatus for geometrical optics where they were divided into four groups performing same set-up simultaneously.

Number of Students			
Grade Level	Control	Experimental	Total
Grade 11	15	16	31

Research instruments. The researcher made use of the localized apparatus made of inexpensive and readily available materials to help facilitate an easy and effective understanding of the concept of geometrical optics. An activity guide was also created to help facilitate the demonstration and the conduct of the experiment.

To test the effectiveness of the localized apparatus in teaching geometrical optics, pretest and posttest was utilized by the researcher. The test questionnaires about the basic concepts of geometrical optics was constructed by the researcher based on a Table of Specification (see Appendices B, C, and D) and was presented to an expert; this is to make sure that the data gathered are consistent and reliable. Furthermore, the researcher considers the test-retest method and Pearson r was used. The experiments and set-up was performed by the researcher prior to the conduct of the study to ensure the reliability of data.

Research procedure. Before the study was conducted, the researcher was able to test the consistency and the accuracy of the data of the localized apparatus using the experiment guide in Appendix I, Appendix J, and Appendix K.

The researcher conducted a dry run to 30 randomly selected non respondent students of Sampiniton Provincial Community High School. Test–retest method was conducted to check the reliability and was presented to an expert to check the validity of the test questionnaires which includes the pretest and the posttest.

Prior to the conduct of the activity, the researcher explained to the grade 11 students the intent of the demonstrations, its purpose, and its importance. Each group demonstrated the concept separately, wherein the controlled group used the conventional ray diagramming technique and the experimental group used the localized apparatus and set-up. The controlled group was divided into four groups and was subjected to plain discussion and ray diagramming technique. On the other hand, the experimental group was subjected to the localized apparatus for geometrical optics where they were divided into four groups performing same set-up simultaneously.(For reference, please see Appendices F to K.)

A pretest was given to both the controlled and the experimental groups. This was done to check the prior knowledge of the learners. After the pretest, the researcher conducted a short introduction and review on the following concepts of geometrical optics, i.e., thin lenses, convex lens; curved mirror, concave mirror; and laws of reflection, for the plain mirror to both the controlled and experimental groups. Subsequently, the researcher let the learners perform the experiment using the set-ups as instructed in the activity guide. An hour was provided in performing the experiment. Within this given time, students were able to perform the procedures as instructed in the experiment guide as well as to answer the questions that were included in the guide. A posttest was conducted to the learners after each

topic is completed. The data that were collected from the activity sheets were computed for accuracy and consistency, while the results of the pretest and the posttest were used to analyze and interpret the learners' performance before and after the experiments and demonstrations.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools that the researcher used in the study are the following:

Accuracy. This was used to determine the closeness of the measurements done by the students when using the inexpensive localized instructional materials to the theoretical value during the demonstrations and experiments.

Standard deviation. This was used to determine the consistency of the data from the learners' use of the inexpensive localized instructional materials during the demonstrations and experiments.

Relative standard deviation. This was used to tell how the different numbers in the data set are scattered around the mean of the pretest and posttest.

Mean .This was used in getting the extent of performance of the learners during their pretest and posttest.

t-test for independent data. This was used in identifying the significant difference between the post-test performance of the experimental group and the control group.

t-test for dependent data. This was used in evaluating the significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of a) experimental group and b) control group.

The proficiency level or academic performance at which the students were performing was based on the following criteria (DepEd Order No. 8, s 2015).

Rating	Verbal Equivalent	Explanation
90% and above	Outstanding	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understanding and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
85%–89%	Very Satisfactory	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
80%–84%	Satisfactory	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75%–79%	Fairly Satisfactory	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
74% down	Did Not Meet Expectations	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Operational Definition of Terms

In order to have a better understanding of this study, relevant terms which are enumerated below are defined according to how they are used in the study.

Accuracy of the data. This refers to the closeness of the measurements attained from the locally made set-up to the true value which can be attained from factory laboratory apparatus.

Consistency of the data. This refers to how effective the locally made set-ups are by measuring how the numbers or data are scattered.

Extent of conceptual understanding. This refers to the students' extent of understanding of the concepts of geometrical optics.

Geometrical optics. This refers to the topic in grade 10 Science Unit 2: Force, Motion, and Energy in Module 3 (Light: Lenses and Mirrors).

Inexpensive demonstrations and experiments. These refer to laboratory activities that utilize readily available materials in the community.

Percentage errors. These are the errors done by the students during the demonstration and experiments.

Chapter II

Presentation, Data Analysis, and Interpretation

This chapter provides information about the accuracy and consistency of the localized apparatus in teaching geometrical optics and pretest and posttest performances of the students before and after their use of localized apparatus in teaching geometrical optics. The chapter actualizes the gathered data through presentation, analysis, and interpretation based on the problems specified in the preceding chapter. The researcher shows the results in tabular and textual forms for better understanding.

Table 1

Data comparison for the accuracy of the three experiments performed by the researcher and the experimental group.

Activity	Percentage of Error				
	Researcher	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
Thin lenses: convex lens					
Thin lens equation	4.84	6.03	7.30	5.80	4.70
Finding the height of the image	4.02	5.07	8.43	8.36	7.26
Law of reflection					
	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Curved mirror: concave mirror					
Curved Mirror equation	1.11	5.27	2.10	7.05	5.71
Finding the height of the image	1.71	6.61	3.62	4.28	2.76

The data in Table 1 shows the comparison for accuracy of the localized apparatus performed by the researcher and the experimental group. It is shown in the table that the researcher shows no error in performing the laws of reflection set-up as reflected in Appendix U. In comparison to the thin lenses, biconcave lens set-up, the researcher marked 4.84 percent in the lens equation as shown in Appendix Z

having the largest percentage of errors among the set-up. Considerably, the results are acceptable since the margin of error for apparatus as performed by the teacher should be less than 5%. Furthermore, the researcher has performed the set-up in numerous trials before it was given and tested by the students to ensure accuracy of the set-up.

On the same table, column 3 to column 6 as performed by group 1 to group 4 show that all four groups got the same percentage of error of 0.00 for the laws of reflection set-up (refer to Appendix T for detailed data presentation), making the set-up very accurate since the acceptable percentage of error is below 10% (Swamy, et.al., 2017).

It can be noted that among the set-ups the thin lenses—convex lens—scored the highest percentage of error (Appendix V, W, X, and Y shows detailed data presentation); this may be caused by unavoidable manipulation, data recording, and construction and calibration error committed by the students while doing the experiment. This is the basis of the consideration stated by Swamy, et.al., (2017) where it was stated that the results of the students in performing the set-up is less than 10% due to some considerable errors that occur due to manufacturing, calibration, or operation of the devices.

It is very important to consider the percentage of error since it determines how big errors are when measuring something in an experiment. Furthermore, it can tell how badly unavoidable errors are in the experiment. Stephanie (2018) stressed that smaller values mean closer to the computed value.

Ng'onomo (2016) emphasized the importance of validity and accuracy of the apparatus used in demonstration and experiments. He stated that validity in research is concerned with the accuracy and truthfulness of scientific findings. He further explained that a valid study should demonstrate what actually exists and that a valid instrument or measure should actually measure what it is supposed to be measured.

Table 2
Data result for consistency of the three experiments

Activity	Sd
Thin lens: convex lens	
Parallel ray	0.24
Thin lens equation	0.07
Finding the height of image	0.1
Law of reflection	0
Curved mirror: concave mirror	
Parallel ray	0.21
Curved mirror equation	0.22
Finding the height of image	0.26

The data in Table 2 show the result for consistency of the three experiments. The data show that the set-up of the activity for the laws of reflection shows great consistency with zero (0) standard deviation as performed by the students. The data reveal that the set-up for the laws of reflection is consistent and thus it shows very reliable results.

The result is supported by the study of Tubog and Piñero (2018) where they concluded that locally constructed apparatus for reflection and refraction of light experiments is accurate and very reliable.

On the other hand, it can be noted that the standard deviation for curved mirror—concave mirror—shows the bigger value compared to other set-ups. This

may be attributed to unavoidable error in data recording specially in recording the distances between the mirror and object and the image and mirror. Mohajan (2017) stressed out that in order to perform a good research, test and data for reliability and validity are needed to be taken very carefully. Macfarlan (2015) claims that it is imperative to be consistent throughout the whole process of collecting data as well as keeping all data as accurate as possible because this will ensure the integrity of any research.

The importance of the reliability and validity of the localized instructional materials was emphasized by Mohajan (2017) where he concluded that reliability and validity of instrumentation are important considerations for researchers in their investigations.

Portney and Watkins (2000) defined reliability as “the extent to which a measurement is consistent and free from error” it is possible to have a high degree of reliability with a low level of validity, but for a research instrument to be valid, it must also be reliable [Keller, 2000].

Table 3
Pretest performance of the students

Group	Mean	Verbal Description	Sd
Control Group (n=15)	68.20	Did Not Meet Expectations	2.83
Experimental Group (n=16)	67.25	Did Not Meet Expectations	2.93

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description
	90% -100%	Outstanding
	85% -89%	Very Satisfactory
	80% -84%	Satisfactory
	75% -79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	Below 75%	Did Not Meet Expectation

Table 3 shows the pretest performance of the students. It can be shown that both the control group (68.20%) and the experimental group (67.25%) fall short on the concept of geometrical optics prior to the conduct of the demonstrations and experiments. The standard deviation of both the control and the experimental group lies close. These figures also indicate that the individual performance of the students is close to the mean. This means that both the control group and experimental group struggle in understanding and have not acquired or developed adequately the prerequisite and fundamental knowledge in the concept of geometrical optics.

The data showed is similar to the findings of Patron (2018) stating that prior to the intervention activity, the overall performance of the students is failing where students fall in “did not meet expectations” level prior to the conduct of the demonstration using localized apparatus.

Table 4
Posttest performance of the students

Group	Mean	Verbal Description	Sd
Control Group (n=15)	80.87	Satisfactory	7.81
Experimental Group (n=16)	90.94	Outstanding	7.28

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description
	90%–100%	Outstanding
	85%–89%	Very Satisfactory
	80%–84%	Satisfactory
	75%–79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	Below 75%	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 4 shows the posttest performance of the students. The data reveal that after the demonstration, the control group earned a mean percentage score of 80.87% which fall under “satisfactory” level. On the other hand, the experimental group achieved the “outstanding” level with a mean percentage score of 90.94%.

The data revealed that the experimental group which is subjected to demonstrations and experiments has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills in the concepts of geometrical optics.

The finding is supported by the study of Olagunju (2000) and Nwike(2013) where the performance of the students showed a positive result after being subjected to intervention activity. The study of Patron (2018) also supports the data. She concluded that the significant difference that exists between the pretest and posttest performances of the students can be attributed to the inexpensive demonstrations and experiments on the concepts of fluid mechanics.

Table 5

Analysis table on the difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students

Group	Pretest	Posttest	Difference	t-value	p-value	Decision/Remark
Control Group (n=15)	68.20	80.87	12.67	6.359	0.000	Reject H_{01} (Significant)
Experimental Group (n=16)	67.25	90.94	23.69	12.636	0.000	Reject H_{01} (Significant)

Level of significance = 0.05

The data in Table 5 reveal that there is a difference of 12.67% between the pretest and posttest performances of the students in the control group. To test the results statistically, t-test for dependent data is applied. It shows that the computed p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This is enough finding to reject the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students. The significant difference exists in the mean scores of the students taught with localized instructional materials and those taught without.

This result relates to the study conducted by Yucor (2018) which reveals that there are significant differences that exist between the pretest and posttest performances of the students after using a localized apparatus in her experiment in teaching cosine laws.

On the other hand, the data also reflect that there is a difference of 23.69% between the pretest and posttest performances of the students in the experimental group. The results further show that the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05); the result is enough to reject the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students. The improvement in their ratings can be attributed to the localized apparatus for geometrical optics.

Similarly, Zarewa (2005) observed that students taught with improvised materials performed better than those taught without such materials in physics. Learners actively participated in the demonstration using the localized apparatus compared to the conventional way of teaching geometrical optics. This observation is supported by the study of Even, et.al. (n.d.), where he concluded that students learn through experimenting wherein geometrical optics is taught in a modern and interactive way. Furthermore, Oladejo, et.al. (2011) revealed that there is a significant difference in the achievement of students taught using standard instructional materials, those taught with improvised instructional material, and those in the conventional instruction.

Table 6

Analysis table on the difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups

Group	Posttest	Difference	t-value	p-value	Decision/Remark
Control Group (n=15)	80.87				
Experimental Group (n=16)	90.94	10.07	3.716	0.000	Reject H ₀₂ (Significant)

Level of significance = 0.05

The data in Table 6 indicate that there is a difference of 10.07 between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups. To test the difference statistically, t-test for independent data is applied. It shows that the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This is enough finding to reject the null hypothesis. This means that a significant difference exists between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups in favor of the latter group. The difference can be attributed to the localized apparatus for geometrical optics that the experimental groups are exposed to.

The data is supported by Clement (2014), where he finds out that the experimental group of students taught with improvised instructional materials shows improvement on their geometry achievement compared to the control group.

The data presented by the researcher contradicts the study of Onasanya and Omosewo (2011) which revealed that the control group and the experimental group shows no significant difference after using the improvised instructional materials in physics.

Chapter III

Summary, Findings, Conclusions, and Recommendations

To give a brief overview of the results of the study, this chapter spells out the summary, findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Restatement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the performance of the students using localized apparatus in teaching geometrical optics to grade 11 students of Sampiniton Provincial Community High School (SPCHS) for the school year 2018–2019

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the accuracy of the set-up in the demonstrations and experiments for:
 - 1.1. Thin lenses: convex lens;
 - 1.2. Curved mirror: concave mirror; and
 - 1.3. Plane mirror: law of reflection?
2. How consistent is the set-up in measuring:
 - 2.1 The focal length of the lens and the mirror;
 - 2.2 The size of the image formed (orientation and the size) by the concave mirror and the convex lens; and
 - 2.3 The angle of reflection in a plane mirror with respect to the angle of incidence?
3. What is the pretest performance of the following groups of students:
 - 3.1 Control group; and
 - 3.2 Experimental group?

4. What is the posttest performance of the following groups of students:
 - 4.1 Control group; and
 - 4.2 Experimental group?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students?
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups.

Summary of Findings

From the data gathered in the study, the following findings of the researcher are presented:

1. Accuracy of the Set-Up in the Demonstrations and Experiments.

The accuracy of the measurements obtained from localized apparatus for the experiments and demonstrations is less than 5% for the researcher and less than 10% for the students.

- 1.1 The average percentage of errors for thin lenses is between 4.02 and 8.43;
- 1.2 For the curved mirror, the average percentage of error is between 1.71 and 7.05; and
- 1.3 For the laws of reflection, the percentage of error is zero (0).

This implies that the localized apparatus was accurate and has exhibited the theory of the concept about geometrical optics.

2. Consistency of the Set-Up.

The data revealed the following standard deviation:

2.1 The focal length of the lens is 0.24 and the focal length of the mirror is 0.21;

2.2 The size of the image formed by concave mirror is 0.26 and the image formed by convex lens is 0.1; and

2.3 The angle of reflection in a plane mirror with respect to the angle of incidence revealed zero (0) standard deviation.

The data presented means that the set-up shows great consistency with its standard deviation closer to the mean. The data reveal that the set-up is consistent, and thus it shows reliable results.

3. Pretest Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups of Students.

The data revealed the following ratings of the students:

3.1 68.20% for the control group; and

3.2 67.25 % for the experimental group.

This means that prior to the conduct of the demonstration of the localized apparatus; the students have less knowledge and skills on the topic geometrical optics.

4. Posttest Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups of Students.

The data revealed the following results of the students:

4.1 80.87% for the control group;

4.2 90.94% for the experimental group.

5. Difference Between the Pretest and Posttest Performances of the Students.

The data revealed a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the students, where the p-values of both the control (0.000) and experimental (0.000) groups are less than the level of significance (0.05); hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

6. Difference Between the Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups.

The data revealed that the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This means that the significant difference exists between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups in favor of the latter group.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study:

1. The localized apparatus used in the experiment is accurate in demonstrating the concepts about geometrical optics.
2. The localized apparatus used in the experiment is consistent in measuring the (a) focal length of the lens and the mirror, (b) size of the image formed by the concave mirror and convex lens, and (c) angle of reflection in a plane mirror with respect to the angle of incidence.
3. The pretest performance of both the control and experimental groups is failing.
4. The posttest performance of the control group is in satisfactory level, while the experimental group is in outstanding level.

5. There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the control group which is in favor of the latter performance. The same finding is revealed considering the experimental group.
6. There is a significant difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups in favor to the latter group.

It can be concluded that the localized apparatus in teaching geometrical optics is effective in improving the performance of the students on the concepts of geometrical optics.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The Department of Education may help in developing teachers' skills by conducting trainings and workshops on the construction and utilization of localized apparatus especially in teaching physics subjects.
2. The Department of Education may promote the utilization of locally constructed apparatus in the experiments and demonstrations in every learning area especially in the fields of science.
3. Teachers will engage the students to demonstrations and experiments where students are exposed to direct manipulation of the localized apparatus so as to develop skills and knowledge in measuring, observing, data recording, and following procedures to lessen systematic and random errors.

4. Teachers may innovate new ways in constructing locally made apparatus, experiments, and demonstration set-up in teaching other concepts of geometrical optics such as concave lens, convex mirror; thin lenses, biconcave lens; and the Snell's law.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A**Graduate School
FOUNDATION UNIVERSITY
Dumaguete City**

September 22, 2018

WILFREDA A. BONGALOS, Ph.D, CESO V

Schools Division Superintendent
Division of Negros Oriental

Ma'am,

Good day!

I am **Andrew Niff E. Balbon**, a student of Foundation University taking up Master of Arts in Education Major in General Science (MAED-Gen.Sci.). I am currently teaching at Sampiniton Provincial Community High School located at Bantolinao, Manjuyod, Negros Oriental.

Right now, I am undergoing a study entitled, "**Localized Apparatus in Teaching Geometrical Optics.**" This is in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Arts in Education major in General Science.

In line with this, I would like to ask permission from your good office to allow me to conduct the study at any working station and to administer pretest and posttest to the grade 11 students, academic year 2018–2019, during their remedial time at 3:45–4:45 pm.

Consequently, the findings of this study shall be used as a basis for crafting learning activities in line with the subject. Your extended support and cooperation will be of a great help to realize this endeavor.

I am looking forward to your favorable response on this humble request. Thank you and more power to you and your administration!

Respectfully yours,

ANDREW NIFF E. BALBON

Researcher

Noted by:

Approved by:

BRANDO PIÑERO, MS-Physics

Thesis Adviser

JASPER ERIC C. CATAN, MAED-English

OIC, M.A.Ed. Program

Letter to the Principal

**Graduate School
FOUNDATION UNIVERSITY
Dumaguete City**

September 22, 2018

JUACRISA D. BALBON

Principal
Sampiniton Provincial Community High School
Bantolinao, Manjuyod, Negros Oriental

Dear Ma'am:

Good day!

I am presently enrolled in the Graduate Studies at Foundation University, Dumaguete City with the degree **Master of Arts in Education major in General Science**.

In line with my research work entitled, "**Localized Apparatus in Teaching Geometrical Optics**," I would like to ask permission from your good office to allow me to conduct laboratory activities and to administer a pretest and posttest to the grade 11 students, academic year 2018–2019. Accordingly, the findings of this study shall be used as a basis for crafting learning activities. Your extended support and cooperation will be of great help to realize this endeavor. Thus, it will forever be appreciated and valued.

I am looking forward to your favorable response on this humble request. Thank you and more power to you and your administration!

God bless.

Respectfully yours,

ANDREW NIFF E. BALBON

Researcher, M.A.Ed-General Science

Noted by:

BRANDO PIÑERO

Thesis Adviser

Approved by:

Jasper Eric C. Catan, M.A.Ed.

OIC, M.A.Ed. Program

APPENDIX B**Table of Specification**Laws of Reflection
Pretest and Posttest

Subject: Science 10

Content area/ tasks	Levels of competency						No. of items	Item placement	Levels of questions		
	Know ledge	Compre hension	Analys is	Applic ation	Evalu ation	Synthe sis			Easy	Av era ge	Diff icul t
Topic: Plane Mirror—Laws of Reflection											
Objectives:											
1. Discuss how light ray is reflected by the plane mirror.		10	8,9				3	8,9,10		1	2
2. State the laws of reflection.	2	1					2	1,2	1	1	
3. Identify the labeled parts in the set-up for laws of reflection.	3,4,5,6,7						5	3,4,5,6,7	5		
Total									6	2	2
Percentage (%)									60	20	20

Prepared by:

Andrew Niff E. Balbon
Science Teacher

APPENDIX C

Table of Specification

Thin Lenses: Convex Lens
Pretest and Posttest

Subject: Science 10

Content area/ tasks	Levels of competency						No. of items	Item placement	Levels of questions		
	Know ledge	Com preh ension	Analysis	Appli cation	Evalu ation	Synthe sis			Easy	Av era ge	Diff icul t
Topic: Thin Lenses—Convex Lens											
Objectives:											
1. Explain how light passes through a convex lens.				8			1	8			1
2. Describe the image produced by thin lenses.	2	4,5	3,9,10	7			7	2,4,5,3,9,10,7	4	3	
3. Solve for the focal length and the image distance.	6						1	6	1		
4. Describe a convex lens.	1						1	1	1		
Total									6	3	1
Percentage (%)									60	30	10

Prepared by:

Andrew Niff E. Balbon
Science Teacher

APPENDIX D**Table of Specification**Curved Mirror: Concave Mirror
Pretest and Posttest

Subject: Science 10

Content area/ tasks	Levels of competency						No. of items	Item placement	Levels of questions		
	Know ledge	Compre hension	Analys is	Applic ation	Evalua tion	Synthe sis			Easy	Av era ge	Diff icul t
Topic: Curved Mirror—Concave Mirror											
Objectives:											
1. Explain how light is reflected from a curved mirror.				10			1	10			1
2. Describe the image produced by curved mirror.	6	1,4,5,7					5	1,4,5,6,7	4	1	
3. Solve for the focal length and the image distance formed by curved mirror.	3						1	3	2		
4. Describe a concave mirror.	2,8,9						3	2,8,9	2	1	
Total									7	2	1
Percentage (%)									70	20	10

Prepared by:

Andrew Niff E. Balbon
Science Teacher

APPENDIX E

**Test Questionnaire for the Study on
“Localized Apparatus in Teaching Geometrical Optics”**

**GEOMETRICAL OPTICS
Pretest/Posttest**

Name: _____ Date: _____

Grade and Section: _____

INSTRUCTION: Read each questions carefully and encircle the letter of the correct answer.

1. Which of the following statements is true about the relationship of the angle of incidence and angle of reflection?

- A. The angle of incident and the angle of reflection are equal.
- B. The angle of incident is greater than the angle of reflection.
- C. The angle of reflection is always greater than the angle of incident.
- D. The angle of reflection is equal to the normal line.

2. According to the second law of reflection, where can the incident ray, the refracted ray, and the normal line be found?

- A. They are scattered at the plane.
- B. They all lie in the same plane.
- C. They all lie at the opposite plane.
- D. Depends on the amount of the incident ray.

For items no. 3 to no. 7, please refer to the figure below.

Figure 1. Reflection of light in plane mirror

3. What is line a?

- A. Incident Ray
- B. Reflected Ray
- C. Normal Line
- D. Mirror

4. What is line b?

- A. Incident Ray
- B. Reflected Ray
- C. Normal Line
- D. Mirror

5. What is line c?

- A. Incident Ray
- B. Reflected Ray
- C. Normal Line
- D. Mirror

6. Which angle is the angle of reflection?

- A. θ_1
- B. θ_2
- C. θ_3
- D. θ_4

7. What is the angle of incidence?

- A. θ_1
- B. θ_2
- C. θ_3
- D. θ_4

8. If the incident ray of light makes a 20° angle, how big will the angle of reflection be?

- A. 20°
- B. 120°
- C. 30°
- D. 600°

9. An incident ray hits a mirror as shown below. What is the angle of reflection?

- A. 40°
- B. 50°
- C. 60°
- D. 90°

10. What happens to a light ray when it strikes a plane mirror? It is _____.

- A. Reflected
- B. Scattered
- C. Regularly Reflected
- D. Irregularly Reflected

11. What type of lens that is thicker at the center than at the edges?
- Concave Lens
 - Convex Lens
 - None of the above
 - All of the above
12. Convex lens are called Converging Lens because:
- The light that passes through it tends to diverge at a particular point called the focal point.
 - The light that passes through it tends to converge at a particular point called the focal point.
 - The light that passes through it tends to converge at the focal length.
 - The light that passes through it tends to diverge at the focal length.
13. In a convex lens, where will you place the object to produce an image twice its size?
- Beyond $2F'$
 - At $2F'$
 - Between $2F'$ and F'
 - At the focal point (F')
14. What should be the position of an object in order to make its highly diminished image at principal focus of a convex lens?
- At infinity
 - Beyond $2F$
 - At $2F$
 - At the focus
15. What should be the position of an object in order to have an image of the same size of the object?
- At infinity
 - Beyond $2F$
 - At $2F$
 - At the focus
16. An image formed by a convex lens is described by which equation?
- $1/f = 1/p + 1/q$
 - $1/p = 1/f - 1/q$
 - $1/q = 1/f + 1/p$
 - $1/q = 1/f - 1/p$

17. What is the characteristic of the image if the object is placed at the focal point (F) of a convex lens?

- A. At a distance f to the right of the lens.
 - B. No image formed
 - C. At a distance $2f$ to the right of the lens.
 - D. At a distance $2f$ to the left of the lens.
18. If an object is 12 cm away from a convex lens of focal length 4 cm, where will the image be?
- A. $q = 6$ cm
 - B. $q = 8$ cm
 - C. $q = 16$ cm
 - D. $q = 3$ cm
19. What are the two types of thin lenses?
- A. biconcave lens and rough lens
 - B. biconcave lens and dual plane lens
 - C. biconvex lens and dual plane lens
 - D. biconvex lens and biconcave lens
20. At which position of object produces an enlarged image formed by convex lens?
- A. At $2F$
 - B. Between the focus F and the V
 - C. At infinity
 - D. Beyond $2f$
21. Where should an object be placed in front of the concave mirror so as to obtain a real image equal to the size of the object?
- A. Beyond the center of curvature C
 - B. At the center of curvature C
 - C. At infinity
 - D. At focus F

22. What are the types of Curved Mirrors?
- Concave mirror and convex mirror
 - Concave mirror and plane mirror
 - Convex mirror and biconcave mirror
 - Convex mirror and plane mirror
33. What is the mirror formula for a concave mirror?
- $1/f = 1/q + 1/p$
 - $1/p = 1/q + 1/f$
 - $1/q = 1/f + 1/p$
 - $1/f = 1/q - 1/p$
24. If the object is at infinity, the distance of the image and the mirror (q) is equal to _____?
- The distance of the object and the mirror
 - The sum of the focal length and the distance of the image (q)
 - The focal length
 - Cannot be defined
25. In a concave mirror, where will the object be placed to produce an image that of the same its size?
- At Focus F
 - At infinity
 - At the center of curvature
 - Beyond the center of curvature
26. What is the nature of image formed by a concave mirror?
- Real and Inverted
 - Real and Upright
 - Virtual and Inverted
 - Virtual and Upright
27. A Concave Mirror produces a diminished image if the position of the object is _____.
- At Focus F
 - At infinity
 - At the center of curvature
 - Beyond the center of curvature

Study the figure below for items 28–29.

28. In Concave Mirror, point A is the _____.
- A. Focal Length
 - B. Focal Point
 - C. Center of the Focus
 - D. Center of Curvature
29. In Concave Mirror, point B is the _____.
- A. Focal Length
 - B. Focal Point
 - C. Center of the Focus
 - D. Center of Curvature
30. Which of the following is the use of a concave mirror?
- A. As reflectors in the head lights of cars
 - B. As side mirror of cars
 - C. "hallway safety mirrors"
 - D. Common mirror at home

Answer Key

1. A
2. B
3. A
4. C
5. B
6. C
7. B
8. A
9. A
10. C
11. B
12. B
13. C
14. B
15. C
16. A
17. B
18. A
19. D
20. B
21. B
22. A
23. A
24. C
25. C
26. A
27. D
28. D
29. B
30. A

APPENDIX F
Construction Guide
Laws of Reflection

A. Materials

Materials	Quantity	Specification	Picture
Marker	1 pc	Any color as long as its visible	
Protractor	1 sheet	Printed on a short bond paper	
Plain mirror	1 pc	9.5 cm x 6.5 cm (or as available)	
Plywood	1 small sheet	3/4 inches thick	
PVC plastics	1 pc	PVC from PVC doors	

Sand paper	1 sheet	120 grains	
Hack saw	1 pc	Size: 12" x 1/2" x 0.6 (18TPI, 24TPI, 32TPI)	
Lighter with flashlight	1 pc	LED	
Batteries	3 pcs	Button batteries (1.5V)	
Pins	4 pcs	Small colored pins	
Glue gun	1 pc	For small glue sticks	

Paint (optional)	1 can	Any color of your choice	
---------------------	-------	-----------------------------	---

B. Procedure

Construction of the lightsource

1. Cut a 10 cm tube from an excess PVC plastic. You should get a 6 cm X 4 cm tube from it.
2. Sand out the excess plastics to make the tube clean and smooth.
3. Cut 2 pcs, 3 cm x 4cm, plastic strip out from PVC.
4. Glue the plastic strip on one end of the PVC tube you cut earlier. Make sure a strip of light can pass through the tube.
5. At the other end of the tube, mount the lighter with flashlight. This will serve as the light source.
6. Paint the lightsource.

Protractor

7. Print a protractor on a short bond paper. This will serve as guide in measuring the angle of reflection.

Mirror

8. Make a stand out of $\frac{3}{4}$ inches plywood. Cut a 5 cm x 5 cm and 5 cm x 6 cm plywood.
9. Join the wood together. As shown in the image.

APPENDIX G

Construction Guide

Thin Lenses: Convex Lens

A. Materials

Materials	Quantity	Specification	Picture
Plywood	1 small sheet	3/4 inches thick	
Sand paper	1 sheet	120 grains	
Flashlight	1 pc	LED	
Mountain dew empty plastic bottle	1 pc	Cut in half (use the upper part of the bottle)	
Screw	1 pc	Small (4mm)	

Screw driver	1 pc	For 4mm screw	
Saw	1 pc	Carpentry saw	
Convex lens	1 pc	Any size and thickness	
Glue sticks	1 pc	Small	
Glue gun	1 pc	For small glue sticks	

Ruler	1 pc	Calibrated with centimeter (cm)	
Electrical tape	1 roll	Black	
Paint (optional)	1 can	Any color of your choice	

B. Procedure

Construction of the screen

1. With a $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood, cut a 6 cm x 6 cm that will serve as your base.

2. Cut another $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood into 6 cm x 2.5 cm block that will serve as a holder.

3. Mount the holder into the base. Make sure it's centered.

4. Cut a $\frac{1}{4}$ inch plywood to a 16 cm x 16 cm board which will serve as the screen. Install the screen into the base as shown in the picture.

5. Sand out the rough surface.

Construction of the convex lens holder

6. With a $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood, cut a 6 cm x 6 cm that will serve as your base.

7. Cut the empty mountain dew bottle in half. As shown in the image.

8. Screw the cap on the base. Make sure it's centered.

9. Glue the convex lens.

10. Sand out the rough surface.

Light source and object

11. With a $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood, cut a 6 cm x 6 cm that will serve as your base.

12. Cut another $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood into 6 cm x 2.5 cm block that will serve as a holder.

13. Mount the holder into the base. Make sure it's centered.

14. Mount the flashlight into the holder.

15. Mount a 2 cm bold arrow on the glass of the flashlight.
16. Sand out the rough surface.

APPENDIX H**Construction Guide****Curved Mirror: Concave Mirror****A. Materials**

Materials	Quantity	Specification	Picture
Plywood	1 small sheet	3/4 inches thick	
Sand paper	1 sheet	120 grains	
Flashlight	1 pc	LED	
Mountain dew empty plastic bottle	1 pc	Cut in half (use the upper part of the bottle)	

Screw	1 pc	Small (4mm)	
Screw driver	1 pc	For 4mm screw	
Saw	1 pc	Carpentry saw	
Concave mirror	1 pc	Any size and thickness	
Glue sticks	1 pc	Small	
Glue gun	1 pc	For small glue sticks	
Ruler	1 pc	Calibrated with centimeter (cm)	

Electrical tape	1 roll	Black	
Paint (Optional)	1 can	Any color of your choice	

B. Procedure

Construction of the screen

1. With a $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood, cut a 6 cm x 6 cm that will serve as your base.

2. Cut another $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood into a 6 cm x 2.5 cm block that will serve as a holder.

3. Mount the holder into the base. Make sure it's centered.

- Cut a $\frac{1}{4}$ inch plywood into a 16 cm x 16 cm board which will serve as the screen. Install the screen into the base as shown in the picture.

- Sand out the rough surface.

Construction of the concave mirror holder

- With a $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood, cut a 6 cm x 6 cm that will serve as your base.

- Cut the empty mountain dew bottle in half, as shown in the image.

- Screw the cap on the base. Make sure it's centered.

- Glue the concave mirror

- Sand out the rough surface.

Light source and object

11. With a $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood, cut a 6 cm x 6 cm that will serve as your base.
12. Cut another $\frac{3}{4}$ inch-thick plywood into a 6 cm x 2.5 cm block that will serve as a holder.

13. Mount the holder into the base. Make sure it's centered.

14. Mount the flashlight into the holder.

15. Mount a 2 cm bold arrow on the glass of the flashlight.
16. Sand out the rough surface.

APPENDIX I

Experiment Guide

This experiment guide will be used to facilitate the demonstrations and experiments for the different concepts of geometrical optics. Please follow discreetly all instructions and precautionary measures from your teacher and write all your answers on this guide sheet.

Plane Mirror: Laws of Reflection

I. Theory

Law of Reflection

The law of reflection governs the reflection of light rays off smooth conducting surfaces, such as polished metal or metal-coated glass mirrors.

Consider a light-ray incident on a plane mirror, as shown in Figure 3. The law of reflection states that the incident ray, the reflected ray, and the normal to the surface of the mirror all lie in the *same plane*. Furthermore, the angle of reflection r is *equal* to the angle of incidence i . Both angles are measured with respect to the normal to the mirror.

Figure 3: The law of reflection

The law of reflection also holds for non-plane mirrors, provided that the normal at any point on the mirror is understood to be the outward pointing normal to the local tangent plane of the mirror at that point. For rough surfaces, the law of reflection remains valid. It predicts that rays incident at slightly different points on the surface are reflected in completely different directions, because the normal to a rough surface varies in direction very strongly from point to point on the surface. This type of reflection is called *diffuse reflection* and is what enables us to see non-shiny objects.

Source: <http://farside.ph.utexas.edu/teaching/3021/lectures/node127.html>

II. Objectives

1. Perform the laws of reflection using localized instructional materials
2. Discuss how light ray is reflected by the plane mirror.
3. State the laws of reflection.

III. Materials

Marker

Protractor(printed on the paper)

Light source

Pins

Plain mirror

IV. Procedure

I. SET-UP

1. Set up the materials as shown below.

Figure 4: Law of reflection

2. Let the light ray hit the point where the normal line and the plain mirror meet (make sure that there is less light to make the laser beam more visible).
3. Measure the angle of the incidence ($\angle i$) from the incident ray to the normal line. *Record the data in Table A (angle of incidence).*
4. Measure the angle of reflection ($\angle r$) from the reflected ray to the normal line. *Record the data in Table A (angle of reflection).*
5. Change the angle of incidence 4 more times to get 5 trials. Repeat procedure numbers 2, 3, and 4.
6. Compute the percentage of difference of the data collected using the formula ($Pd = (\text{bigger value} - \text{smaller value} / \text{bigger value}) \times 100\%$). *Record the data in Table A (percentage difference).*

V. Data and Results

Table A

Trials	Angle of Incidence	Angle of Reflection	Percentage Difference (Pd= (bigger value - smaller value / bigger value) x 100%)
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			

VI. Analysis

1. What will happen to the angle of reflection if the angle of incidence will increase?
2. What will happen to the angle of reflection if the angle of incidence will decrease?
3. Where can we find the normal line, incident ray, and reflected ray?
4. How does the angle of incidence compare to the angle of reflection?

APPENDIX J

Thin Lenses: Convex Lens

I. Theory

A lens which is thinner at the edges and thicker at the center is known as convex lens. Generally lenses are made up of glass or transparent plastic, and the same can be used for transmitting, refracting, or focusing the light.

A convex lens is supposed to be made up of a number of prisms with the base of each prism toward the center of the lens. When rays parallel to the principal axis pass through a convex lens, they are bent inward. The point at which they converge is known as the principal focus.

The distance from the principal focus to the center of the lens is known as the focal length. This type of lens bends the light inward. The types of convex lens are double convex, plano-convex, and concavo-convex.

In optics and photography, **infinity focus** is the state where a lens or another optical system forms an image of an object in an infinite distance away. This corresponds to the point of focus for parallel rays. The image is formed at the focal point of the lens.

An example of a convex lens is a magnifying glass. When an object is placed closer to a convex lens than the principal focus, the rays never converge and magnified image is formed on the same side of the object. Thick, bulging convex lenses have the shortest focal lengths, which are commonly used as powerful magnifying glasses.

Taken from: <http://www.icoachmath.com/physics/definition-of-convex-lens.html> (September 14, 2017)

II. Objectives

The objectives of this experiment are the following:

1. Explain how light pass through a thin lens.
2. Describe the image produced by thin lenses.
3. Solve for the focal length and the image distance

III. Materials

Screen	Light bulb and socket
Convex lens with lens holder	Slit
Plywood (3/4 and 1/4)	Nails
Empty Plastic bottle	Screws
Ruler	

IV. Procedure

A. Set-up

1. Assemble the set-up as shown below.

Figure 1: Optical Bench (Thin Lenses)

B. Parallel ray method

2. Adjust the light source such that it is in line with the axis of the lens. Do this by projecting a shadow of the slit on the screen (the slit is 2cm tall). A shadow projected at the center indicates that the light source is correctly positioned.

3. Project a clear image of the object from a distance (infinity) on the screen. Adjust the lens until a clear image is achieved. Measure the distance of the screen to the lens (q) and get the focal length (f) of the lens using the lens equation ($1/f = 1/p + 1/q$) Let $p = \infty$. *Record your answer in Table A.*

C. Using thin lens equation method

4. Project a clear image of the slit on the screen. Adjust the slit until a clear image is achieved. Measure the distance of the lens from the slit (p) and from the screen to the lens (q) and get the focal length (f) of the lens using the lens equation ($1/f = 1/p + 1/q$). *Record the result of the computed value of the focal length (f) column in Table B.*
5. To get the experimental value of (f), measure the distance between the lens and the image projected on the screen using a ruler. *Record the data in the experimental value of focal length (f) column in Table B.*
6. Repeat the procedure numbers 4 and 5. Adjust the distance between the lens and the slit (p) and the distance between the screen and the lens (q). Make 3 more trials and get the average computed focal length and experimental focal length. *Record your answer in Table B.*
7. Determine the percentage error of the data gathered using the formula ($\% \text{ error} = (\text{computed value} - \text{experimental value} / \text{computed value}) \times (100\%)$). *Record the result in the percentage error column in Table B and get the average percentage error of the trials.*

D. Finding the height of the image

8. To get the experimental value of the image height (h'), measure the image projected on the screen using a ruler. *Record the data in the experimental value of image height (h') column in Table C.*
9. Using the data gathered in tables A and B, solve the computed value of image height (h') in each trial using the formula $h' = qh/p$ (whereby image height (h') = 2cm). *Record your answer in the computed image height column in Table C.*

V. Data and Results

a. Using parallel ray method

Trial	Distance of the Slit and Lens (p)	Distance of the Screen and Lens (q)	Focal Length
1	Infinity(∞)		
2	Infinity(∞)		
3	Infinity(∞)		
Average:			

b. Using thin lens equation method

Trial	Distance of the Slit and Lens (p)	Distance of the Screen and Lens (q)	Focal Length (Computed) ($1/f = 1/p + 1/q$)	Focal Length (Experimental)	Percentage Error (%error = (computed value - experimental value) / computed value) X (100%)
1					
2					
3					
Average:					

c. Finding the height of the image

Trial	Distance of the Slit and Lens (p)	Distance of the Screen and Lens (q)	Image Height (h') (Computed)	Image Height (h') (Experimental)	Percentage Error (%error=(computed value - experimental value/computed value) X (100%))
1					
2					
3					
		Average:			

VI. Data Analysis

1. Describe the image formed in the convex lens based on its location, orientation, size, and type.
2. At what distance can you produce a clear image? Why?
3. Explain how light passes through a convex lens (converging lens).

APPENDIX K

Curved Mirrors: Concave Mirror

I. Theory

A **curved mirror** is a mirror with a curved reflecting surface. The surface may be either *convex* (bulging outward) or *concave* (bulging inward). Most curved mirrors have surfaces that are shaped like a part of a sphere, but other shapes are sometimes used in optical devices. The most common non-spherical types are the parabolic reflectors, found in optical devices such as reflecting telescopes that need to image distant objects, since spherical mirror systems, like spherical lenses, suffer from spherical aberration. Distorting mirrors are used for entertainment. They have convex and concave regions that produce deliberately distorted images.

II. Objectives

The objectives of this experiment are the following:

1. Explain how light is reflected by a curved mirror.
2. Describe the image produced by a curved mirror.
3. Solve for the focal length and the image distance reflected by curved mirror.

III. Materials

Screen	Light bulb and socket/used
Flashlight	Batteries
Convex mirror with holder	Ruler
Plywood (3/4 and 1/4)	

Empty soda plastic bottle

IV. Procedure

A. Set-up

1. Assemble the set-up as shown below. (Top view)

Figure 2: Optical bench (curved mirror)

2. Cut an A-shaped object that will fit to the glass of the light source (flashlight). Paste it in the glass.
3. Place the concave mirror at an angle. Make sure that an image will form at the screen (as shown in Figure 1).

B. Using parallel ray method

4. Project a clear image of the object from a distance (infinity) on the screen. Adjust the mirror until a clear image is reflected on the screen. Measure the distance of the screen to the mirror (q). Get the focal length (f) of the lens using the mirror equation ($1/f = 1/p + 1/q$); let $p = \infty$. Make 3 more trials of this step. *Get the average focal length of the trials. Record the data in Table A.*

C. Using curved mirror equation method

5. Project a clear image of the A-shaped object on the screen. Adjust the screen until a clear image is achieved. Measure the distance of the mirror from the object (A-shaped object) (p) using a ruler. Then, measure the distance from the screen to the curved mirror (q) and get the focal length (f) of the mirror using the lens equation ($1/f = 1/p + 1/q$). *Record the result of the computed value of the focal length (f) in Table B.*
6. To get the experimental value of the focal length, measure the distance between the image and the mirror. *Record the data of experimental value of the focal length in Table B.*
7. Repeat the procedure numbers 5 and 6. Adjust the distance between the mirror and the object (p) and the distance between the screen and the mirror (q). Make 3 more trials and get the average focal length.
8. Determine the percentage error of the data gathered using the formula ($\% \text{ error} = (\text{computed value} - \text{experimental value} / \text{computed value}) \times 100\%$). *Record the result in the Percentage Error Column in Table B and get the average percentage error of the trials.*

C. Finding the height of the image

9. Using the data gathered in tables A and B, solve the computed value of image height (h') in each trial using the formula $h' = qh/p$ (whereby image height (h') = 2cm). *Record your answer in the Computed Image Height column in Table C.*

V. Data and Results

a. Using Parallel Ray Method

Trial	Distance of the Object and the Curved Mirror (p)	Distance of the Screen and the Curved Mirror (q)	Focal Length
1	Infinity(∞)		
2	Infinity(∞)		
3	Infinity(∞)		
		Average:	

b. Using Curved Mirror Equation Method

Trial	Distance of the Object and the Curved Mirror (p)	Distance of the Screen and the Curved Mirror (q)	Focal Length (Computed)	Focal Length (Experimental)	Percentage Error (%error=(computed value – experimental value/computed value) X (100%))
1					
2					
3					
		Average:			

c. Finding the Height of the Image

Trial	Distance of the Object and the Curved Mirror (p)	Distance of the Screen and the Curved Mirror (q)	Image Height (h') (Computed)	Image Height (h') (Experimental)	Percentage Error (%error=(computed value - experimental value/computed value) X 100%)
1					
2					
3					
		Average:			

VI. Data Analysis

1. Describe the image formed in the concave mirror based on its location, orientation, size, and type.
2. At what distance can you produce a clear image on the screen? Why?
3. Explain how light is reflected through a concave mirror.

APPENDIX L

Lesson Plan

Republic of the Philippines
 Department of Education
 Region VII, Central Visayas
Division of Negros Oriental
 Sampiliton Provincial Community High School

Lesson Plan in Science 10

Section and Time: Grade 11			
Learning competency	Predict the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of the images formed by plane mirror. S10FE-IIg-50	Level	10
		Quarter	2
Learning objectives	Knowledge: State the laws of reflection Skills : Perform the laws of reflection Attitudes : Display correctness in labeling the components in a reflection Plane	Week No.	6
		Day	3
Topic	Reflection of Light	Duration	1 hour
Resources needed	LCD projector, laptop, activity sheet, pen, improvised reflection apparatus.		

Procedure

Element of the Plan	Suggested Activity
Awareness	Video presentation: The students will watch a video on the reflection of light.
Activity	Individual activity: Reflection of light The student will answer an activity sheet provided by the teacher entitled "Plane Mirror: Laws of Reflection"
Analysis	1. What is reflection? 2. What are the different components of reflection?
Abstraction	Reflection is the bouncing off of light ray when it strikes or hits a surface like a plane mirror. The components of reflection are (a)incident ray, the ray of light

	<p>approaching the mirror represented by an arrow approaching an optical element like mirrors;(b)reflected ray, the ray which leaves the mirror and is presented by an arrow pointing away from the mirror;(c)normal line,an imaginary line that can be drawn perpendicular to the surface of the mirror at the point of incidence where the ray strikes the mirror.</p>
Application	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What happens when light is reflected? 2. How can one that reflects back form a positive image of oneself?
Assessment	<p>Before the lesson is presented to the class, a pretest will be given to the students. <i>(See attached pretest.)</i></p> <p>After the lesson, a formative assessment will be given to the students. <i>(See attached formative assessment.)</i></p>
Assignment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Read in advance the activity “Mirror, Mirror, on the Wall”on page 173 of LM Science 10.
Remarks	

APPENDIX M

Republic of the Philippines
 Department of Education
 Region VII, Central Visayas
Division of Negros Oriental
 Sampiniton Provincial Community High School

Lesson Plan in Science10

Section and Time:			
Learning competency	Predict the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of the images formed by thin lenses. S10FE-IIg-50	Level	10
		Quarter	2
Learning objectives	Knowledge: Describe the image produced by thin lenses. Skills : Solve for the focal length and the image distance of the object. Attitudes: Justify how image is produced by thin lenses.	Week No.	7
		Day	1
Topic	Thin lenses: convex lens	Duration	1 hour
Resources needed	LM Science 10, plane mirror, laser pen/laser pointer, paper protractor, improvised thin lens apparatus		

Procedure

Element of the Plan	Suggested Activity
Awareness	Video presentation: A video about how convex lenses are used in the industry and in other places.
Activity	Group activity: Reflection of light in convex lens In this activity the students will describe how an image is produced in a convex lens. They will also solve for the focal length and the image distance reflected by convex lenses.(See activity sheet attached.)
Analysis	3. How is the image in the convex lens being formed?
Abstraction	Idea: The image formed in a convex mirror is always virtual and erect, whatever the position of the object may be.

<p>Application</p>	<p>Answer the illustration using the ray diagramming technique.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p>3.</p>
<p>Assessment</p>	<p>Before the lesson is presented to the class, a pretest will be given to the students. <i>(See attached pretest.)</i> After the lesson, a formative assessment will be given to the students. <i>(See attached formative assessment.)</i></p>
<p>Assignment</p>	<p>Reflection of light is employed significantly in making optical instruments like periscopes. Research how light travels in a periscope.</p>
<p>Remarks</p>	

APPENDIX N

Republic of the Philippines
 Department of Education
 Region VII, Central Visayas
Division of Negros Oriental
 Sampiniton Provincial Community High School

Lesson Plan in Science 10

Section and Time:			
Learning competency	Predict the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of the images formed by curved mirrors. S10FE-IIg-50	Level	10
		Quarter	2
Learning objectives	Knowledge: Describe the image produced by curved mirror. Skills: Solve for the focal length and the image distance reflected by curved mirror. Attitudes: Justify how light is reflected by a curved mirror.	Week No.	7
		Day	1
Topic	Image formation in curved mirrors	Duration	1 hour
Resources needed	LM Science 10, plane mirror, laser pen/laser pointer, paper protractor, improvised apparatus for concave mirror		

Procedure

Element of the Plan	Suggested Activity
Awareness	Video presentation: A video about how concave mirrors are used in the industry and in other places.
Activity	Group activity: Reflection of light in a concave mirror In this activity the students will describe how an image is produced in a concave mirror. They will also solve for the focal length and the image distance reflected by curved mirror. <i>(See activity sheet attached.)</i>
Analysis	1. How is an image in the concave mirror being formed?
Abstraction	Idea: The image formed by a concave mirror is real and inverted regardless of the position of the object.

<p>Application</p>	<p>Answer the illustration using the ray diagramming technique.</p>
<p>Assessment</p>	<p>Before the lesson is presented to the class, a pretest will be given to the students. <i>(See attached pretest.)</i> After the lesson, a formative assessment will be given to the students. <i>(See attached formative assessment.)</i></p>
<p>Assignment</p>	<p>Discuss how dentists use concave mirrors.</p>
<p>Remarks</p>	

APPENDIX O

Concave Mirror

Data results of the experiment for curved mirror performed by group 1

Parallel ray method						
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)			
1	Infinity	7.6	7.60			
2	Infinity	8.5	8.50			
3	Infinity	8	8.00			
	Average:		8.03			
Curved mirror equation method						
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error	
1	22	11.5	7.55	8	5.96	
2	12.5	18.3	7.43	8	7.67	
3	12	22.5	7.83	8	2.17	
	Average:		7.60	8	5.27	
Finding the height of the image						
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	Height of the image (experimental)	% error	
1	26	55	4.23	4.6	8.75	
2	34	65	3.82	4	4.71	
3	30	40	2.67	2.5	6.37	
	Average:				6.61	

APPENDIX P

Data results of the experiment for curved mirror performed by group 2

Parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and mirror	Distance of the screen and mirror (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	Infinity	7.50	7.50		
2	Infinity	7	7.00		
3	Infinity	8	8.00		
		Average	7.50		
Curved mirror equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and mirror (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and mirror (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error
1	13	18	7.55	7.50	0.66
2	12	20	7.50	7.50	0
3	11	20	7.10	7.50	5.63
		Average:	7.38	7.50	2.10
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and mirror (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and mirror (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	height of the image (experimental)	% error
1	37	38	2.05	2.10	2.44
2	36	51	2.83	2.60	8.13
3	31	51	3.29	3.30	0.30
		Average:			3.62

APPENDIX Q*Data results of the experiment for curved mirror performed by group 3*

Parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	Infinity	6	6		
2	Infinity	8	8		
3	Infinity	7	7		
		Total:	7		
Curved mirror equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error
1	9	21.5	6.34	7.00	10.41
2	10	18	6.43	7.00	8.86
3	11	16.5	6.60	7.00	6.06
		Average:	6.46	7.00	8.45
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	Height of the image (experimental)	% error
1	9	26	5.78	5.80	0.35
2	10	27	5.40	5.90	9.26
3	11	29	5.27	5.10	3.23
		Average:			4.28

APPENDIX R*Data results of the experiment for curved mirror performed by group 4*

Parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	Infinity	7.5	7.5		
2	Infinity	8.5	8.5		
3	Infinity	8	8		
Average:			7.8		
Using curved mirror equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error
1	11	23.5	7.49	7.8	4.14
2	10.5	24	7.3	7.8	6.85
3	12	27	8.31	7.8	6.14
Average:			7.7	7.8	5.71
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	Height of the image (experimental)	% error
1	11	23.5	4.27	4.5	5.39
2	10.5	24	4.57	4.6	0.66
3	12	27	4.50	4.6	2.22
Average:					2.76

APPENDIX S*Data results of the experiment for curved mirror performed by the researcher*

Using parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	infinity	7.60	7.60		
2	infinity	7.50	7.50		
3	infinity	7.30	7.30		
4	infinity	7.20	7.20		
5	infinity	7.00	7.00		
6	infinity	7.40	7.40		
7	infinity	7.40	7.40		
8	infinity	7.30	7.30		
9	infinity	7.10	7.10		
10	infinity	6.90	6.90		
		Average:	7.27		
		Sd	0,21		
Using thin lens equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	Percentage Error
1	10.00	27.2	7.31	7.27	0.57
2	10.00	25.8	6.94	7.27	4.82
3	10.00	25.6	6.88	7.27	5.64
4	10.00	27	7.26	7.27	0.16
5	10.00	28	7.53	7.27	3.41
6	10.00	27.3	7.34	7.27	0.94
7	10.00	25.8	6.94	7.27	4.82
8	10.00	25.6	6.88	7.27	5.64
9	10.00	26.8	7.20	7.27	0.91
10	10.00	27.1	7.28	7.27	0.21
		Average:	7.16	7.27	2.71
		sd	0.22		
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	Height of the image (experimental)	Percentage Error
1	10.00	27.2	5.44	5.7	4.78
2	10.00	25.8	5.16	5.2	0.78
3	10.00	25.6	5.12	5.2	1.56
4	10.00	27	5.4	5.6	3.70
5	10.00	28	5.6	5.8	3.57
6	10.00	27.3	5.46	5.6	2.56
7	10.00	25.8	5.16	5.1	1.16
8	10.00	25.6	5.12	5.0	2.34
9	10.00	26.8	5.36	5.4	0.75
10	10.00	27.1	5.42	5.6	3.32
		Average:	5.32	5.42	2.452
		Sd	0.26		

APPENDIX T*Data results of the experiment for law of reflection performed by the four groups*

	Trials	Angle of incidence	Angle of reflection	% difference
Group 1	1	50	50	0
	2	40	40	0
	3	30	30	0
	4	20	20	0
	5	10	10	0
Group 2	1	40	40	0
	2	50	50	0
	3	60	60	0
	4	90	90	0
	5	80	80	0
Group 3	1	80	80	0
	2	40	40	0
	3	20	20	0
	4	90	90	0
	5	70	70	0
Group 4	1	50	50	0
	2	30	30	0
	3	50	50	0
	4	40	40	0
	5	20	20	0

APPENDIX U

Data results of the experiment for law of reflection performed by the researcher

Trial	Angle of incidence			
	20	30	40	50
	Angle of reflection			
1	20	30	40	50
2	20	30	40	50
3	20	30	40	50
4	20	30	40	50
5	20	30	40	50
6	20	30	40	50
7	20	30	40	50
8	20	30	40	50
9	20	30	40	50
10	20	30	40	50
Sd	0	0	0	0

APPENDIX V*Data results of the experiment for thin lens—convex lens—performed by group 1*

Parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	Infinity	9	9.00		
2	Infinity	10	10.00		
3	Infinity	11	11.00		
		Average	10.00		
Using thin lens equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error
1	17	27	10.43	10	4.12
2	28	18	10.96	10	8.76
3	16	31	10.55	10	5.21
		Average:	10.65	10	6.03
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	Height of the image (experimental)	% error
1	17	25	2.94	3.2	8.84
2	17	28	3.29	3.5	6.38
3	20	20	2.00	2	0
		Average:			5.07

APPENDIX W*Data results of the experiment for thin lens—convex lens—performed by group 2*

Parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	Infinity	9	9.00		
2	Infinity	5	5.00		
3	Infinity	4	4.00		
		Average	6.00		
Thin lens equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error
1	9	15	5.62	6	6.67
2	7	24	5.42	6	10.7
3	12	11	5.74	6	4.53
		Average:	5.59	6	7.3
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	height of the image (experimental)	% error
1	8	15	3.75	4	6.66
2	7	24	6.86	7.5	9.33
3	12	11	1.83	2	2.29
		Average:			2.54

APPENDIX X*Data results of the experiment for thin lens—convex lens—performed by group 3*

Using parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	Infinity	10.5	10.5		
2	Infinity	11	11		
3	Infinity	10	10		
	Average		10.5		
Thin lens equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error
1	20	23	10.7	10.5	1.87
2	21.5	28	12.16	10.5	13.65
3	20	23	10.7	10.5	1.87
	Average:		11.19	10.5	5.80
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	Height of the image (experimental)	% error
1	20	23	2.3	2.5	8.69
2	21.5	28	2.6	2.8	7.7
3	20	23	2.3	2.5	8.69
	Average:				8.36

APPENDIX Y

Data results of the experiment for thin lens—convex lens—performed by group 4

Parallel ray method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)		
1	Infinity	11	11		
2	Infinity	10	10		
3	Infinity	12	12		
		Average	11		
Thin lens equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	% error
1	16	32	10.67	11	3.09
2	20	21	10.24	11	7.42
3	15	21	11.41	11	3.59
		Average:	10.77	11	4.7
Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	Height of the image (experimental)	% error
1	16	32	4	4.3	7.5
2	20	21	2.1	2.3	9.52
3	25	21	1.68	1.6	4.76
		Average:			7.26

APPENDIX Z

Data results of the experiment for thin lens—convex lens—performed by researcher

Using parallel ray method			
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens	Distance of the screen and lens (cm)	Focal length (cm)
1	Infinity	10.00	10.00
2	Infinity	10.20	10.20
3	Infinity	10.10	10.10
4	Infinity	10.50	10.50
5	Infinity	10.60	10.60
6	Infinity	10.00	10.00
7	Infinity	10.20	10.20
8	Infinity	10.10	10.10
9	Infinity	10.70	10.70
10	Infinity	10.20	10.20
		Average:	10.26
		SD:	0.24

Using thin lens equation method					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Focal length (computed) in (cm)	Focal length (experimental) in (cm)	Percentage Error
1	16.2	28.3	10.3	10.26	0.39
2	16.2	28.1	10.23	10.26	0.29
3	16.2	28.4	10.34	10.26	0.77
4	16.2	28.7	10.45	10.26	1.82
5	16.2	28.2	10.27	10.26	0.10
6	16.2	28.3	10.3	10.26	0.39
7	16.2	28.6	10.41	10.26	1.44
8	16.2	28.3	10.3	10.26	0.39
9	16.2	28.6	10.41	10.26	1.44
10	16.2	28.1	10.23	10.26	0.29
		Average:	10.32	10.26	0.73
		SD	0.07		

Finding the height of the image					
Trial	Distance of the slit and lens (p) in (cm)	Distance of the screen and lens (q) in (cm)	Height of the image (computed)	height of the image (experimental)	Percentage Error
1	16.2	28.3	3.5	3.6	2.86
2	16.2	28.1	3.47	3.3	4.9
3	16.2	28.4	3.51	3.4	3.13
4	16.2	28.7	3.54	3.6	1.69
5	16.2	28.2	3.48	3.6	3.45
6	16.2	28.3	3.49	3.5	0.27
7	16.2	28.6	3.53	3.6	1.98
8	16.2	28.3	3.49	3.5	0.29
9	16.2	28.6	3.53	3.6	1.98
10	16.2	28.1	3.47	3.4	2.02
		Average:	3.501	3.51	2.257
		SD	0.10		

APPENDIX AA**Curriculum Vitae****Personal Profile**

Name: Andrew Niff E. Balbon
 Date of Birth: November 30, 1989
 Place of Birth: Manjuyod, Negros Oriental
 Home Address: Sundo-an, Manjuyod, Negros Oriental

Educational Background

Graduate Studies: Master of Arts in Education Major in General
 Science
 Foundation University

Tertiary: Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in
 Biological Sciences
 Negros Oriental State University
 March 2010

Secondary: Majuyod National High School
 Manjuyod, Negros Oriental
 March 2006

Elementary:Manjuyod Central School
 Manjuyod, Negros Oriental
 March 2002

Others: National Certificate II in:

- Massage Therapy
- Housekeeping

 Technical Education and Skills Development
 Authority
 Dumaguete City
 January 2015

Work Experience: Junior High School Science Teacher
 Department of Education
 May 15, 2013–to date
 Science Teacher

Korean Faithful Christian Pilgrims, Inc.
 June 2010–April 2013

Examinations Passed:

Licensure Examination for Teachers
September 2010